

Supplementary Information

European Modes of Circulation Variability

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Fig. S1 Silhouette analyses of inter/intra cluster similarity for Wards clusters on 2–30 clustering levels, delimited for combined SOM models based on different numbers of original trained SOM neural networks

Fig. S2 Mean annual anomalies in 200 hPa geopotential heights (a) and 850 hPa geopotential heights (b) for four basic European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in 1981–2023 period

Fig. S3 Mean temperature anomalies in four basic European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY) in the 1981–2023 period

Fig. S4 Mean precipitation anomalies during the European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY) in the 1981–2023 period

Fig. S5 Mean daily soil moisture change for four basic modes of European circulation variability (EMoCs) in the summer half-year (SHY) and the winter half-year (WHY) in the 1981–2023 period

Fig. S6 Seasonal absolute and relative frequencies of the four basic European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in the 1940–2023 period, with 10-year Gaussian smoothing (dashed)

Fig. S7 Mean temperature anomalies during individual European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in (a) 1940–1957, (b) 1958–1980 and (c) 1981–2023 periods

Fig. S8 Mean precipitation anomalies during four basic European modes of circulation variability (EMoCs) in (a) 1940–1957, (b) 1958–1980 and (c) 1981–2023 period